

ISic3286

I.Sicily inscription 3286

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε κίτε

2. Εὐτυχίς ζή[σα]

3. σα ἔτη ν τελε[υ]

4. τᾷ τῆ̄ πρὸ ε ἰ,δ(ῶν) [---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

Here lies Eutychis, having lived for 50 years, died 5 days before the ides of...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645554

PHI 316268

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 186
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Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia.
Vatican. At no.415

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